

Workshop held Lincoln University, 27 November 2015

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Beneath the surface: nutrient loss from soils Colin Gray (AgResearch)

How good are NZ soils? Allan Hewitt (Landcare Research)

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**Structure and connection below the root zone: implications for transport in alluvial gravel systems
Murray Close and Lee Burberry (ESR)**

**Back to the future: what are our long-term soil quality issues Ogi Mojsilovic and Jeromy Cuff (Environment
Canterbury)**

Cropping – how best to use our soil resource Nick Pyke (Foundation for Arable Research)

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Introduction

Trish Fraser (Plant & Food Research)

Celebrating Soils in the Hub is a one day workshop following an 11 presentation series. It recognises the International Year of Soils, World Soils Day (5th December 2015) and also incorporating the 2015 Norman Taylor Memorial lecture.

United Nations - Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) declared 2015 as International Year of Soils with the aim: To increase awareness and understanding of the importance of soil for food security and essential ecosystem functions.

IYS 2015 Key messages

- Healthy soils are the basis for healthy food production.
- Soils are the foundation for vegetation which is cultivated or managed for feed, fibre, fuel and medicinal products.

- Soils support our planet's biodiversity and they host a quarter of the total.
- Soils help to combat and adapt to climate change by playing a key role in the carbon cycle.

- Soils store and filter water, improving our resilience to floods and droughts.
- Soil is a non-renewable resource; its preservation is essential for food security and our sustainable future.

Norman Taylor Memorial Lecture 2015

Prof Richard McDowell
AgResearch

Beneath the surface: nutrient loss from soils Colin Gray (AgResearch)

[Slides](#)

How good are NZ soils? Allan Hewitt (Landcare Research)

On James Cook's first voyage (1770) around the South Island, naturalist Joseph Banks observed the tall timbered forests and noted that "The size of the plants ... especially the timber trees ... sufficiently evinced the richness of the soil" He applied a European rule-of-thumb that related big trees to fertile soil. This later proved to be wrong and Banks' rule was termed the "biometric fallacy". The early optimism however, was taken up by other promoters of the new colony, and although debunked, the historian Tom Brooking stated that "we still have this reverberating ideal of the fertility of the land" The question of how good are New Zealand soils is still an open question, and an important one. So what is the truth?

There are three approaches to answer the question. First, the national Land Use Capability Classification categorises our land into 8 capability classes. The highest category (class 1) land which is highly versatile for intensive arable cropping only occupies about 5.2% of our total land area. Second, the national high class soils classification identifies a comparable area of similar quality soils. Third, a soil natural capital stocks assessment under development identifies the adequacy of our soils to support the soil functions needed by highly performing land use enterprises. Evidence from these approaches suggest; 1, we have some very highly performing, versatile, high class soils but they are of minor area, 2, even where soils are not highly productive they can offer high performance services to natural and agro-ecosystems, 3, in principle any soil can be considered good soil if it provides the soil stocks needed by a specified enterprise. As we accumulate good knowledge of the potentials and risks of our soils, and if we factor into this our production system (people, technology, infrastructure, education, and governance), then there is hope that we can capitalise on the combination of the soils we have plus good management. Our soils can then work for us despite their limitations.

Because our high class soils are of modest area, they must not be overlooked. These irreplaceable, high performing, versatile resources are locally, nationally, and internationally important for New Zealand and must be preserved and utilised wisely.

Soil as a driver of sustainable increases in forest productivity
Simeon Smaill (Scion)

[Slides](#)

Structure and connection below the root zone: implications for
transport in alluvial gravel systems
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Cropping – how best to use our soil resource
Nick Pyke (Foundation for Arable Research)

Key issues facing the cropping industry in relation to soils include:

- Soil Nitrogen (N) mineralisation,
- Nutrient movement in soils and uptake,
- Soil microbes – good, bad and ugly,
- Composts, manures, cover crops
- Farm practices to maximise soil quality
- Understanding the vadose zone
- Monitoring and mapping
- Extension

Although we have a good understanding of the amount of N needed for many of the crops we grow and when the crops need N, it is not possible to accurately apply the quantity of N required by the crop as N is constantly being mineralised in the soil. A methodology that predicts the N available from the soil in the growing season to the crop would result in more accurate application of fertiliser N to meet plant needs and reduce the risk of N loss from soils.

Simple to complex nutrient budgets can be used to estimate plant needs and the timing of N. There is also a good understanding of the rooting depth of many crops but the ability of plants to extract N from different depths is not well known. Similarly there is good information on how N moves down the soil profile and this can be predicted using a simple equation but this information has rarely been used in developing good policy for nutrient management.

Yields of crops are often severely below optimum due to the presence of soil borne diseases and there are limited management practices designed to reduce the incidence of these diseases. We often have good knowledge on the disease but will have limited information on how the soil characteristics (biotic and abiotic) impact on disease and little or no information on how soils impact on beneficial soil microorganisms.

Practices, such as the use of composts, are rarely used in broad acre cropping as they are not considered viable and the benefits they infer may often be minimal when measured over limited timeframes. Similarly we have limited information on how practices such as irrigation influence soil characteristics although there is information on how valuable irrigation is in improving nitrogen use efficiency and therefore reducing leaching risk. While there is a significant amount of international literature on the impact of cultivation practices on both soils and crop performance this information is often selectively interpreted in relation to New Zealand and complete documentation of the cultivation trials undertaken in New Zealand is required to ensure the full range of cultivation practices are used effectively in the future.

Ongoing concern about N loss to the groundwater has increased the demand for knowledge of what happens in the vadose zone. Although there was a significant research programme on the vadose zone the knowledge derived from this work needs to be delivered to industry and regulators to ensure any policies are informed by quality science. Further, if ongoing research is required this needs to occur.

Increasingly farmers are required to supply information in relation to their farm practices. The starting point for this is usually a farm map which also includes a soil map. The use of S-map is likely to be increasing important for nutrient management and reporting and it is essential it is readily available and compatible with a range of models or use requirements.

Farming, and particularly cropping, is totally reliant on the soil resource and good management practices will help protect and manage the soil resource and water quality. To ensure farmers, third party professionals and regulators are effectively and sustainably managing the soil resource for current and future farming improved extension is needed in relation to soils. It is critical that people with the knowledge and skills are trained and resourced to ensure the practitioners have the techniques and the knowledge available to manage soils for the future.

Soils for resilient dairy farming systems

David Chapman (Dairy NZ)

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How can plants help reduce nitrogen loss from farms?

Roshean Woods (Lincoln University)

New Zealand dairy systems are typically pasture-based where cattle graze outdoors year-round. During grazing, cows deposit urine onto the paddock. This represents an input of nitrogen (N) into the soil-plant system greater than the amount that the pasture plants can use. The nitrogen which is not

used by the plants is often lost from the soil in drainage water. For this reason, N leaching is a significant environmental concern in intensively grazed NZ pasture-based systems.

Perennial ryegrass-white clover mixtures are commonly used on New Zealand dairy farms. However, these plants do not grow very fast during the cooler seasons (late autumn to early spring). Therefore demand for water and nitrogen by these plants is low, and the risk of nitrogen loss to water is high during these times of the year. The use of alternative pasture plants could help reduce this nitrogen loss to water through increased uptake of urinary nitrogen. A lysimeter study was conducted to measure pasture growth and nitrogen loss to water beneath alternative pastures: Italian ryegrass and lucerne, compared with perennial ryegrass-white clover. Results showed a reduction in N leaching loss beneath Italian ryegrass pasture compared with perennial ryegrass-white clover pasture. Although, this was not reflected by higher annual pasture yield, Italian ryegrass had higher winter N uptake which may have contributed to the lower leaching loss. Once complete this study will help determine whether alternative pasture types could be used by New Zealand dairy farmers to reduce their nitrogen losses and thereby reduce their negative impact on the environment.

When being told to P-off is good

Richard McDowall (AgResearch)

Norman Taylor Memorial Lecture

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